

PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11-STEM SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN EARTH AND LIFE SCIENCE EXPOSED TO DIFFERENT INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

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Abstract. This study aims to determine the level of performance of Grade 11-STEM Senior High School learners in Earth and Life Science exposed to different types of instructional materials. Learners in the Control and Experimental Group showed the same level of performance before their exposure to different types of instructional materials as revealed by the pre-test results. After exposure to different types of instructional materials, there is a significant difference in the performance of the learners in the Experimental Group based on the post-test results. Based on the pre-test and post-test results for both groups of Grade 11-STEM learners showed significant differences in their performance using traditional and STAR BOOKS-contained instructional materials.

Keywords. Life Earth Science, Instructional Materials, Starbooks

1 Introduction

The teacher plays a vital role in the development of the “brain and body” of the learners and such as she is duty-bound to make sure that they are at the right pace of learning. The use of instructional materials plays a pivotal role in enhancing the learning experience for learners across various education settings. When appropriately integrated into teaching strategies, instructional material can make complex concepts more accessible, cater to diverse learning styles, and foster a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Instructional materials play a big role in the performance of learners in the classroom. These are considered the factors that make up the pyramid of learners: the teacher, the lesson, and the instructional materials. Despite this age of technology most instructional materials used in teaching and learning activities are considered traditional (Wiley, 2017).

In today's diverse educational landscape, a balanced approach that integrates traditional and digital instructional materials is crucial. Educators should leverage the strengths of each medium to create a comprehensive and engaging learning experience for learners, taking into consideration the benefit of hands-on activities, and visual aids, ongoing research will guide educators in optimizing the use of both traditional and digital instructional material (Gee, 2014).

Another form of instructional material being provided by STARBOOKS is a stand-alone information source designed to reach learners who have access to the internet, STARBOOKS-contained instructional material consists of hundreds of thousands of digital science and technology resources in various formats (text, and video/audio) placed in specially designed “pods” set a user-friendly interface.

Since the STARBOOKS kiosk is available in the library, the researcher who is a teacher and at the same time the librarian in the Basic Department focused on this study which aimed to determine the performance of Grade 11-STEM learners in Earth and life Science exposed to different types of instructional materials.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

This study determines the level of performance of Grade 11-STEM senior high school learners in Earth and Life Science exposed to different types of instructional materials in San Carlos College-Basic Education Department during the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of Grade 11-STEM learners in Earth and Life Science based on the pre-test result before exposure to:
 - a. Traditional instructional, and
 - b. STARBOOKS-contained instructional material?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the Control and Experimental groups based on the pre-test results?
3. What is the level of performance of the Grade 11-STEM learners as revealed by the post-test result after exposure to:
 - a. Traditional instructional materials and
 - b. STARBOOKS-contained instructional material?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups as revealed by the post-test result?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of each group as revealed by the pre-test and post-test results?

1.2 Scope and Delimitation

The purpose of the study is to determine the effects of traditional and STARBOOKS instructional material on the performance of Grade 11-STEM learners in Earth and Life Science during the first quarter covering the topics based on DepEd's Curriculum Guide. Said topics are the following: Life on Earth is Possible, Earth System Science, Compositional Layers of Earth, Rock, Geologic Processes on Earth's Surface, Big Bang Theory, Introduction to Earth System Science, and Rock-forming Minerals.

2 Review of Related Literature

The call for understanding things and phenomena around us is a must. Specifically, the concept of teaching science at the senior high school level, particularly on the STEM strand. Although the fundamental object of science teaching is to help learners develop their maximum human potential so that they may become productive and contributing citizens in the free society, certain operation changes are imperative from time to time if the objectives are to serve as a realistic guide for helping learners develop and learn most effectively. Man lives in a world surrounded by products of science, this world must necessarily be inhabited by people who think critically and scientifically (Janssen, 2015).

The good academic performance of learners at the Senior High School is of paramount importance in every educational system. It is highly significant to note that a human being's entire existence is commonly based on the amount of knowledge he or she acquires, and how much this knowledge is utilized in developing himself, his country, and the world at large. This explains the reason underlying the need for education. The basic thing that one gets from education is knowledge. One gets to know about various things ranging from Mathematics to History, Literature to Political Science. The worldly knowledge we gain from education plays a great role in our future lives and helps us to understand in a much more cohesive manner. Meanwhile, educational success is a measure of the academic performance of learners.

According to Kua (2016), school plays a great role in society by supplying an individual with information enough to last him a lifetime. The school must assist learners to become scientifically liberated; they must be taught how to interpret information that they will encounter in the future. Thus, educational experiences are the "heart and soul" of learning the structure of the discipline.

In addition, Kua further stated that since the primary concern of education is to assist learners in developing their potential to the optimum, it becomes imperative that studies and innovation be continually undertaken to identify the different causes of failure in school.

Based on the philosophy of John Dewey, learning is good when it provides learning experiences or situations that will ensure understanding. Good teaching requires a rich environment of instructional materials and devices that will challenge the

attention of the learners, stimulate thinking, and facilitate understanding which could make learning more meaningful (Manuel,2017). At the same time, Dewey emphasized that teaching is good when the method used is supplemented by another method and instructional device. This is based on the principle that the best learning occurs when more senses are stimulated and utilize the process.

Teaching is no longer a simple process of telling and giving out information by lecturing and checking out assignments (Anderson, 2018). An effective and successful teacher has to be motivating, managing, guiding, and assisting the learners as they learn. She often works with individual learners and holds remedial classes with small groups as they go about their learning; as a professional worker, the teacher shall at times endeavor to assist them in gaining knowledge and skills that would become their tools in the future.

Custodio (2019) said that effective teaching calls for alternative strategies to accomplish different goals. No single approach to teaching works well in all situations. Changing trends and approaches, varying methods and techniques, as well as new tools and devices, should be used inside the classroom. Teaching science should introduce more techniques, and topic processes that are relevant to the learners' life and environment that would interrelate science, technology, and society.

Balang (2019) proposed enrichment instruction materials for the use of learners in Science 6. The study delved into the attributing factors that led to unsatisfactory results in teaching science due to the inadequacy of the teacher in the preparation and use of instructional materials, insufficient books, and lack of laboratory facilities.

The study conducted by Layno (2018) determined the effectiveness of computer-assisted instruction in Science 7. Fifty (50) Grade 7 learners were the subject of the study. Using the quasi-experiment method of research, the result showed that computer-assisted instruction facilitates learning and makes learning more meaningful, and the use of audio-visual materials initiates the curiosity and interest of the learners.

Another study conducted by Alonzo (2019) sought to find different areas in science that were satisfactorily realized and attained. Using Science 6 teachers as respondents, it was found that there were inadequate materials and resources. This problem met by the teacher-respondents was serious so they achieved their science objectives on a satisfactory level only. It was recommended that the use of instructional materials could help enhance the learners in science.

Falcon (2020) determines the problems encountered by science teachers in Agusan del Norte, and through the gathered data most serious problem encountered by the respondents was the inadequacy of instructional materials in the subject. It was recommended that science teachers should design their supplementary instructional materials to meet their learning objectives in science.

In the same vein, Pena (2020) conducted a similar study in Butuan City and recommended that science teachers should be provided with up-to-date teaching guides and relevant audio-visual materials. Also included in the recommendation is that if the needed instructional materials are not readily available the teachers should design and prepare low-cost instructional materials for learners.

The study conducted by Lucas (2019) in the San Juan District revealed that the serious problems encountered by science teachers were a lack of textbooks and other teaching aids and difficulty in securing materials in consonance with the teaching guides.

Another study conducted by Cabrera (2021) focused on Grade 6 Science one of the recommendations made was the preparation of instructional materials and the use of these should be in the light of curriculum needs and special requirements like enrichment, remedial, and review.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher made use of the descriptive and quasi-experimental methods of research. It is a research design where a comparison will be made, as in an experiment, but no random assignment of participants to a group occurs. The behavior of the respondents will be measured both before and after the treatment or condition is implemented. Although the independent variable can be manipulated, the respondents will not be randomly assigned to conditions or order of conditions.

The one-shot design was employed wherein a pre-test and post-test were administered and the significant difference in the performance of the two groups was determined.

3.2 Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at San Carlos College Basic Education Department, Mabini St., San Carlos City, Pangasinan. The 40 Grade 11 STEM learners were used as respondents of this study. The learners were divided into two (2) groups based on the final grades in science in Grade 11. The Control Group was exposed to traditional instructional materials and the Experimental group was exposed to the use of STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A survey questionnaire was disseminated to faculty members to assess their needs related to innovative teaching strategies.

3.4 Statistical Treatment of Data

To obtain valid and reliable results from the data gathered, appropriate statistical tools were employed.

To answer sub-problems 1 and 3, means and mean percentage scores were used to determine the learner's level of performance in Earth and Life Science in the pre-test and post-tests.

Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Equivalent
85-100	Mastery (M)
71-84	Closely Approximately Mastery (CAM)
57-70	Moving Toward Mastery (MTM)
43-56	Average Mastery (AM)
29-42	Low Mastery (LM)
15-28	Very Low Mastery (VLM)
0-14	Absolutely No Mastery (ANM)

To answer sub-problems 2 and 4, t-tests for independent samples with correlated means were employed. To answer sub-problem 5, a t-test for dependent samples with uncorrelated means was used.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Performance of Grade 11 STEM Learners in the Pre-Test Before Exposure to Traditional Instructional Materials and STARBOOKS-Contained Instructional Materials

Table 1 shows that both control and experimental groups obtained almost the same means and mean percentage scores. The performance of the two (2) groups is described as average mastery. Whereas, the mean percentage scores obtained by both groups are way below the Department of Education's prescribed master level of 75%.

It could be deduced that there is a need to enhance the level of performance of Grade 11 STEM learners in Earth and Life Science. To improve their performance, they must be properly guided and provided with appropriate instructional materials.

Table 2. Pre-Test Results of Control and Experimental Groups in Earth and Life Science
 N=40

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	DE
Control	46.86	44.50	AM
Experimental	16.59	43.87	AM

4.2 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in the Pre-Test

It could be gleaned from Table 2 that based on the computed t-value of 0.509 it is lower than the critical value of 0.615. Therefore, it could be deduced that there is no significant difference in the performance of both groups in the pre-test in Earth and Life Science. Hence, it is proven that the Control Group and Experimental Group have the same level of performance, therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the performance of both groups as revealed by the pre-test results is hereby accepted.

The findings of this study reveal that there is a need to make use of appropriate materials to enhance the performance of Grade 11 STEM learners in Earth and Life Science. This further supports the state of Kua (2016) that teachers should be encouraged to use instructional materials for gainful teaching-learning encounters.

4.3 Performance of Control and Experimental Groups in the Post-Test

Table 3 presents the post-test results in terms of means and mean percentage scores. The same table shows that the Experimental Group obtained a higher mean (31.90) than the Control Group (24.53). The mean percentage scores show a big difference as shown in Table 3. The level of performance of the Control Group in the post-test in Earth and Life Science is described as moving toward master (MTM) while the Experimental Group's level of performance is described as closely proximately mastery (CAM).

Table 3. Post-Test Results of Control and Experimental Groups in Earth and Life Science
 N=40

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	DE
Control	24.53	58.04	MTM
Experimental	31.90	76.20	CAM

4.4 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in the Post-Test

Table 4 presents the difference in their level of performance using a t-test of uncorrelated means. The same table shows that the mean difference of both groups is 7.37. Findings show that the computed t-value is 8.29 and the critical t-value is 0.001. This result manifests that the significant level is very much lower than the computed t-value, therefore, the null hypothesis is a result of this rejected. Based on the data in the table, there is a significant difference between the performance of the Control Group exposed to traditional instructional materials and the Experimental Group exposed to STARBOOKS-contained instruction materials.

It could be deduced further that the experimental group exposed to STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials has a higher level of performance in Earth and Life Science based on the results of the post-test administered after the try-out.

Table 4. Test of Significance in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in the Post-Test

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Decision
Control	24.53	7.37	8.29	0.001	Reject H_0
Experimental	31.90				

4.5 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Post-Test

Table 5 shows the findings on the difference in the performance of the Control Group based on the pre-test and post-test results. The mean difference in the pre-test administered to the Control Group is 7.67. Based on the computed t-value and the critical t-value, it could be gleaned that the former is higher than the latter. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the performance of the Control Group based on the pre-test and post-test results is hereby rejected.

Table 5. Test of Significance in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-Test and Post-Test

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Decision
Control	16.86	4.67	5.123	0.011	Reject H_0
Experimental	24.53				

It could be concluded that based on the reflected data in the same table, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Control Group after their exposure to traditional instructional materials. It could be surmised that the use of appropriate instructional materials is advantageous to the learners.

4.6 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Post-Test

It could be gleaned in Table 6 that the mean difference between the pre-test and post-test is 15.32. Further reflected in the same table that the computed t-value which is 17.802 far exceeded the critical t-value of 0.011, therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the performance of the Experimental Group based on the pre-test and post-test results is rejected. The rejection of the null hypothesis leads to the conclusion that there is a significant difference in the performance of the Experimental Group exposed to STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials.

Table 6. Test of Significance in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-Test and Post-Test

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Decision
Control	16.58	15.32	17.802	0.011	Reject H_0
Experimental	31.90				

The results reflect that the STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials have noted advantages to empower learners to enhance their performance and lead to their academic success. Based on these data, the learners' enhanced performance could pave the way to their high performance as evidenced by the results of the post-test.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the pre-test results both Control and Experimental groups have the same level of performance described as an average mastery in Earth and Life Science. There is no significant difference in the performance of both groups based on their pre-test result in Earth and Life Science. The level of performance based on the post-test results in Earth and Life Science, the Experimental Group is described as closely approximately mastery, while the Control Group is described as moving toward mastery. There is also a significant difference in the performance of both the Control and Experimental Groups in Earth and Life Science based on the post-test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the Control Group as revealed by the pre-test and post-test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the Experimental Group based on the pre-test and post-test results.

Science teachers should use a variety of instructional materials suited to the needs and interests of the learners. Teachers should determine the level of performance of the learners in their subjects periodically. The STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials should be used by science teachers in the teaching-learning activities. Teachers in other fields of specialization should use the STARBOOKS-contained instructional materials in their classes. School heads should conduct in-service training for teachers focused on the development of instructional materials. Similar studies should be conducted focused on other factors not included in this study.

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